

Immunohistochemical Analysis of Vascular Changes in Psoriasis Vulgaris Using CD 34 in Tertiary Health Care Center in Haryana

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Abstract:

Angio (neo) genesis is an important phase in the pathogenesis of psoriasis vulgaris and CD 34, a molecule expressed on endothelial cells play an important role in this important step. In this cross sectional study among 60 non-infectious erythematous papulosquamous skin disorders, 28 cases histopathologically diagnosed as psoriasis vulgaris were kept for CD 34 immunohistochemical analysis for study of vascular changes.

Result and Conclusion: Among 28 histopathologically confirmed cases of psoriasis vulgaris which were subjected to CD 34 immunohistochemical marker study, 11 cases show strong positivity, 13 cases show moderate positivity and 4 cases show weak positivity. CD 34 is an essential angio genesis marker and has revealed the enlarged cutaneous vasculature associated with psoriasis. As a result specific therapies directed against CD 34 can be developed in future which can offer better disease control.

Keywords: Angio (neo) genesis, Endothelial cells, CD 34.

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Introduction

Angio (neo) genesis is an important phase in the pathophysiology of psoriasis, after inflammation and epidermal hyperproliferation. The inflammatory environment significantly modifies the function of vascular endothelial cells by causing the induction and activation of many proangiogenic factors like CD34,

1. Adhesion and migration of inflammatory cells
2. Angiogenesis: psoriasis is characterized by enhanced cutaneous vasculature, and CD34 is a crucial angiogenesis marker. IHC (immunohistochemistry) can be used to determine the severity of CD34 expression in psoriasis. [4]
3. Microvessel density (MVD): CD34 is used to determine Microvessel density in psoriasis, which has been found to be significantly higher in involved and uninvolved skin of psoriasis compared with normal skin. [5]

Aim and Objectives: To study the vascular changes in skin biopsies reported histopathologically as psoriasis vulgaris by using CD 34 immunohistochemical marker.

Material and Methods

A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted for one year (January 2023 to December 2023) in the Department of Dermatology and Pathology at Maharaja Agrasen Medical College, Agroha (Hisar), Haryana.

The study comprised of 60 cases of histologically diagnosed different non-infectious, erythematous skin diseases who initially presented in department of dermatology where VEGF, CD31, Nerve Growth Factor (NGF), and Von Willebrand Factor (vWF). [1,2]

CD34 is 110-kDA transmembrane glycoprotein which is primarily expressed in endothelial cells, stem cells, splenic marginal zone, sweat glands, nerves, hair follicles, muscle bundles, vessels and on dendritic interstitial cells. [3]

In psoriasis, CD34 plays the following roles,

Inclusion Criteria:

- All patients with clinical suspicion/diagnosis of non-infectious erythematous papulosqua-

- Adequate biopsy (3-5mm in size)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients are suggestive of having infectious skin lesions.
- Inadequate biopsy.

The interpretation of CD34 staining was done by viewing the three highly vascularized areas in a 40X field and counting the number of vessels.

Single or clusters of endothelial cells, with or without lumen, were considered as individual ves-

sels and scored as follows⁶:

- Mild/ weak :04-10 capillaries
 - Moderate :11-20 capillaries
 - Severe/ strong: 21-28 capillaries
- lesional biopsy was taken and sent to department of pathology for histopathological confirmation. Out of 60, 28 cases were histopathologically diagnosed with psoriasis and its variants which were further kept for CD34 immunohistochemistry for the study of vascular changes.

Figure 1: Immuno-histochemical staining with CD34 antigen. Multiple blood vessels depict CD34 strong expression. (40X)

Results: Biopsy material from 28 histopathologically confirmed cases of psoriasis vulgaris and its variants were subjected to the immuno-histochemical marker CD34. Out of 28 cases, 26 patients were diagnosed histopathologically as psoriasis vulgaris, and 2 patients as acrodermatitis continua of hallopeau (ACH).

Table 1: CD34 scoring in cases of psoriasis and its variants (n=28)

CD34 Scoring	Count	Percentage
Weak	4	14.3%
Moderate	13	46.4%
Strong	11	39.3%

And from above 28 cases, 11 cases (39.3%) showed strong positivity for CD34, while 4 cases (14.3%) of psoriasis depicted weak positivity. And majority i.e. 13 cases (46.4%) showcased moderate positivity. Both cases of Acrodermatitis continua of hallopeau (ACH) expressed strong positivity.

Figure 2: Age correlation with CD34 scoring (n=28)

Fig. no. 2 depicts the correlation of age groups with CD 34 scoring in psoriatic patients.

Maximum patients i.e. 9 were affected in the 41-50 years age group and followed by 7 patients in age group 21-30 years. None of patients showed positivity for CD 34 less than 10 years of age while

among geriatric cases; 3 patients showcased positivity.

Statistical analysis: The data was input into an Excel sheet which was further analysed with SPSS Software version 20.0 with appropriate statistical tests.

Table 2: Gender correlation with CD34 expression (n=28)

CD 34 Scoring	Gender	No. of Patients	Percentage
Weak	Female	0	0 %
	Male	4	100.0%
Moderate	Female	4	30.8%
	Male	9	69.2%
Strong	Female	2	18.2%
	Male	9	81.8%

Table no. 2 depicts that out of 13 cases with moderate expression of CD34, males 9 (69.2%) outnumbered females 4 (30.8%). Out of 4 cases with weak expression, only males showed positive expression (100%) while amongst 11 cases of strong expression, again males 9 (81.8%) outnumbered females 2 (18.2%).

Discussion:

Table 3: CD 34 Expression

Studies	Total Cases	CD 34 Expression		
		Mild	Moderate	Strong
Basher et al [4]	80	17(21.3%)	50(62.5%)	13(16.3%)
Amin et al [6]	14	3(21.4%)	7(50%)	4(28.6%)
Javed et al [7]	64	13(20%)	39(61%)	12(19%)
Shankar et al [8]	32	0(0%)	23(72%)	9(28%)
Present study	28	4(14.3%)	13(46.4%)	11(39.3%)

A study was done by Basher et al⁴ which exhibited the CD 34 expression frequency. In his study, moderate staining of CD34 expression were found in 50 (62.5%) cases, mild staining in 17 (21.3%) patients, and strong staining in 13 (16.3%) patients. Whereas our study expressed moderately (46.4%), strongly (39.3%), and weakly (14.3%) in psoriasis vulgaris but strongly expressed in acrodermatitis continua of hallopeau (variant of psoriasis).

Conclusion

We discovered that the majority of psoriasis patients showed moderate staining expression of CD34. The essential angiogenesis marker has revealed the enlarged cutaneous vasculature associated with psoriasis. As a result it can assist in understanding the diverse histogenesis and development of specific therapies directed against CD 34 in future.

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